

NEW COMPOUNDS OF GALLIUM. PART IV. GALLIUM
HYDROXYL AMMONIUM ALUM AND DOUBLE
SULPHATES OF GALLIUM AND PRIMARY,
SECONDARY AND TERTIARY
ALIPHATIC AMINES.

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Gallium sulphate has been combined with hydroxylamine sulphate and sulphates of primary, secondary and tertiary aliphatic amines. Hydroxylamine has yielded an alum crystallising from water with 24 molecules of water. The double sulphates containing amine sulphates contain less than 24 molecules of water, some containing 16 and others 18 molecules. Double sulphates of two primary, one secondary and two tertiary amines have been obtained.

Soret (*Arch. Phys. nat.*, 1888, 20, 528) prepared gallium ammonium alum by combining gallium sulphate and ammonium sulphate. In this paper, gallium sulphate has been combined with hydroxylamine sulphate and sulphates of primary, secondary and tertiary aliphatic amines. Hydroxylamine has yielded with gallium sulphate an alum crystallising from water with 24 molecules of water. The double sulphates containing amine sulphates contain less than 24 molecules of water of crystallisation. Double sulphates of two primary, one secondary and two tertiary amines have been obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Gallium Hydroxyl-Ammonium alum.—Equimolecular quantities of gallium sulphate and hydroxylamine sulphate were mixed together in aqueous solutions and then evaporated in a vacuum desiccator. The solid obtained was dissolved in the least quantity of water and the double sulphate precipitated by means of absolute alcohol. It was crystallised several times from water. Crystals were large and found, after drying for two days in air, to contain 24 molecules of water. It effloresces when kept exposed to the air for a long time. It is insoluble in alcohol. [Found: N, 2.95, Ga, 13.24; SO_4 , 37.12. $\text{NH}_2(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$, $\text{Ga}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$, $24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 2.73; Ga, 13.67; SO_4 , 37.5 per cent].

Gallium isoAmylammonium Sulphate.—To a molecule of gallium sulphate dissolved in water, an aqueous solution of a little more than a molecule of isoamylamine sulphate was added. The mixture was allowed to evaporate in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid till a dry solid was obtained. It was treated with absolute alcohol and the free amine sulphate, which is soluble in alcohol, was removed by filtration. The residue was dissolved in the smallest quantity of water and the double sulphate precipitated by the addition of absolute alcohol. It was crystallised from water

and analysed after drying in air. The double sulphate is soluble in water but insoluble in alcohol, ether and other common organic solvents. On keeping, it gradually became insoluble in water. It melts with decomposition at a high temperature. [Found: N, 2.7; Ga, 14.52; SO₄, 38.48. (C₆H₁₁NH₂)₂, H₂SO₄, Ga₂(SO₄)₃, 16H₂O requires N, 2.83; Ga, 14.17; SO₄, 38.86 per cent].

Gallium isoButylammonium Sulphate.—The double sulphate was prepared in the same way as the above compound. In properties it is similar to that compound. [Found: N, 2.75; Ga, 14.91; SO₄, 40.22. (C₄H₉NH₂)₂, H₂SO₄, Ga₂(SO₄)₃, 16H₂O requires N, 2.91; Ga, 14.58; SO₄, 40 per cent].

Gallium Diethylammonium Sulphate.—An aqueous solution of a molecule of diethylamine sulphate was mixed with a little more than a molecule of gallium sulphate dissolved in water and the mixed solution was evaporated in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid. The solid obtained was treated with absolute alcohol. The double sulphate being soluble in alcohol went into solution. It was separated by filtration from gallium sulphate which is insoluble in absolute alcohol. The filtrate on evaporation gave deliquescent crystals of the double sulphate which was crystallised from water before analysis. It is very soluble in water but insoluble in acetone, ether, chloroform etc. This double sulphate also melts with decomposition at a high temperature. [Found: N, 2.97, Ga, 14.46; SO₄, 38.80. {(C₂H₅)₂NH} 2H₂SO₄, Ga₂(SO₄)₃, 18H₂O requires N, 2.81; Ga, 14.05; SO₄, 38.55 per cent].

Gallium Tri-isoamylammonium Sulphate.—A molecule of gallium sulphate dissolved in water was mixed with a little more than a molecule of tri-isoamylamine sulphate and allowed to evaporate in vacuum over sulphuric acid. The dry sulphate was treated with absolute alcohol to remove the free amine sulphate and then crystallised twice from water. The compound was analysed after drying between the folds of filter papers. It decomposes on keeping and becomes insoluble in water. [Found: N, 2.19; Ga, 10.68; SO₄, 29.81. {C₈H₁₇N} 2H₂SO₄, Ga₂(SO₄)₃, 16H₂O requires N, 2.20; Ga, 11.02; SO₄, 30.28 per cent].

Gallium trimethylammonium sulphate was obtained in the same way as the tri-isoamylammonium sulphate. It is very soluble in water. [Found: N, 3.35; Ga, 14.92; SO₄, 39.28. {(CH₃)₃N} 2H₂SO₄, Ga₂(SO₄)₃, 18H₂O requires N, 2.89; Ga, 14.46; SO₄, 39.67 per cent].